

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: global		Date: 01/2025	
Number: 0	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 1	Scale: 1:10	Material: _	Treatment: _
Draw by: CH + NA			

PIECE NAME	QTY
#box	1
#dual_water_bottle	1
#roof	1
#single_water_bottle	2
#camera_and_DEL_pa nel	1

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: Global		Date: 01/2025	
Number: 0	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 1	Scale: 1:10	Material: _	Treatment: _
	Draw by: CH + NA		

1:10

DETAIL A

scale 1 : 2

1:5

ARTICLE	PIECE NAME	QTY
1	001_Box_Rako_90L	1
2	braket	4
3	016_passage_flange	2
4	0121_light_cover_small	2
5	ISO 10669-8.8-N	6
6	0122_light_cover_big	2
7	ISO 4017 - M8 x 20-N	6
8	ISO - 4034 - M8 - N	6

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: Box		Date: 01/2025	
Number: 0	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 1	Scale: 1:10	Material: _	Treatment: _
Draw by: CH + NA			

COUPE B-B
ECHELLE 1 : 5

ARTICLE	PIECE NAME	QTY
1	016_roof_Xrails_structure	1
2	010_small_side_panel	2
3	012_top_panel	2
4	Ass_angleElcom	8
5	011_long_side_panel	2
6	013_panel_light_trap	2
7	grove_nuts_M6	16
8	014_setting_plate	4
9	M6_x16_hexagonal_co untersunk_screw	8

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: Roof		Date: 01/2025	
Number: 0	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 1	Scale: 1:5	Material: _	Treatment: _
Draw by: CH + NA			

ARTICLE	PIECE NAME	QTY
1	020_water_bottle	1
2	023_cap_tube	1
3	021_Xrail_bottle	2
4	grove_nuts_M6	4
5	0211_bottle_holder	1
6	027_fixing_jumper_1	2
7	O-ring	1
8	clamping_square_6	2
9	screw_CHC-BTR_6x12	4

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: single water bottle		Date: 01/2025	
Number: _	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 2	Scale: 1:5	Material: _	Treatment: _
Draw by: CH + NA			

ARTICLE	PIECE NAME	QTY
1	020_water_bottle	2
2	023_cap_tube	2
3	021_Xrail_bottle	2
4	0211_bottle_holder	2
5	025_fixing_jumper_2	1
6	027_fixing_jumper_1	2
7	O-ring	2
8	grove_nuts_M6	7
9	clamping_square_6	3
10	021_Xrail_bottle	1
11	screw_CHC-BTR_6x12	7

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: dual water bottle		Date: 01/2025	
Number: 0	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 1	Scale: 1:5	Material: _	Treatment: _
	Draw by: CH + NA		

ARTICLE	PIECE NAME	QTY
1	screw_CHC-BTR_2x6	4
2	M6_x16_hexagonal_co untersunk_screw	4
3	screw_CHC-BTR_6x10	1
4	screw_CHC-BTR_3x8	2
5	#camera E3V revB with lens	1
6	ISO 4762 M4 x 6 - 6N	2
7	034_connector_nuts	2
8	033_connector_male_2ways	2
9	LED_M375D4	1
10	LED_M450D4	1
11	032_lens_light_trap	1
12	030_angle_camera	1
13	LED_M530D3	1
14	031_LED_camera_panel	1

Piece: _		Inquirer: FP	
Assembly: LED and camera panel		Date: 01/2025	
Number: 0	Emplacement: _		
Qt: 1	Scale: 1:2	Material: _	Treatment: _
Draw by: CH + NA			